

Managing Product Features and Customer Satisfaction via Product Development, Product Branding, and Product Packaging: Evidence from CWAY Table Water

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ABSTRACT

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Customer satisfaction has become a source of worry to most organizations, including the table water business. The table water industry is one of the most competitive markets in Nigeria today and due to its portability and affordability, it is seen as a lucrative trade to venture into. However, this has also led to the proliferation of mushroom table water companies and has made it difficult for some companies to maintain their customer base. Therefore, this study examines the effect of product features on customer satisfaction of veritas table water. The population of this study comprised of 3037 customers of CWAY Table Water Abuja, Nigeria. The sample size of 353 was derived through Taro Yamane's sample size formula. Data for this study was collected using a structured questionnaire. Descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used for data analysis. The findings from the study revealed that product development and features have positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. It was generally concluded that product features have significant effect on the customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. This study recommends there should be very strong emphasis on the development of new and innovative products, the management of CWAY Table Water to embrace all the indicators of product branding to be able optimally maximize its benefits and embrace innovative ideas, monitoring and responding to the changes in the needs of the customers.

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Introduction

Customer satisfaction is one of the keystone concepts in strategic marketing. Its determinants and consequents have been rather well studied over the last 30 years. Not only do academicians admit the importance of customer satisfaction for a firm's development but also practitioners and businessmen pay great attention to its measurement and management. The intuition behind the view that customer satisfaction is important is straightforward. Satisfied customers tend to demonstrate loyal behaviour (Balinado et al., 2021, Oyenuga et al., 2020). The customers prefer the firm to its competitors, customers are less price sensitive and old customers attract new customers through word-of-mouth. Ultimately customer satisfaction through loyalty leads to higher revenues and to better financial performance.

The ability of a firm to attract new customers while maintaining the existing ones (Oyenuga et al., 2019) better than its competitors is said to be having a competitive edge. According to Temeltas and Kaya (2021) a firm's approach to business, and the steps it uses to grapple with competition and strengthen its share in the market, constitutes a firm's competitive strategies. For this reason, a company must be very prompt in coming up with superior strategies so as to fully exploit the new opportunities better than its competitors. Thus, the firm has to focus in creating tomorrow's competitive advantages faster than competitors mimic the ones it poses today. The approach used by an organization to gain a competitive hedge entails both defensive and offensive measures.

Competitive strategies mainly deal with plans and policies that managers use to make an organization to provide greater customer value hence giving it an ability to compete successfully (Liu & Atuahene-Gima, 2018). For this reason, competitive strategies are often viewed as limited in scope relative to business strategies. According to Porter (2008), there are five business strategies that can be adopted by organizations to gain competitive advantage. The five strategies relate to the extent to which the scope of a business' activities is narrow versus the broad and the extent to which a business seeks to differentiate its products. Among the competitive strategies is the differentiation strategy, which this study will focus on.

Product features encompasses value addition to the product by introducing additional features that can attract customers. Customers are often willing to pay an extra shilling arising from the additional features that are added to a product. For this strategy to be successful, the market should enable proper segmentation based on the product features. Companies can implement the product features by focusing on the tastes, reliability of the product, features of the product, uniqueness and stature (Bayraktar et al., 2017). The successful implementation of this strategy is greatly dependent on the activities that are carried out in the value chain therefore within the value chain each stage must have proper value addition framework.

The various ways of applying the product features include product development, product branding and product packaging. Product development is a product features that is executed at product level. According to Supiandi (2021), by incorporating strategy at the product level, the brands can distinguish themselves from the similar products in the markets and customers will view the products differently. Product branding is a long-term marketing support for a brand, which is based on how the characteristics of the consumers being targeted are defined (Bayraktar et al., 2017). It entails a proper comprehension of the customers' brand inclinations and the prospects from the brand. It is a plan for the development of a flourishing brand with

an aim of realizing specific objectives. Product packaging is the procedure used in ensuring that products are well protected, well stored, distributed, sold and used (Pratono, 2018). Packaging is a synchronized system of preparing goods for transport, logistics, warehousing, selling and the ultimate use.

Customer satisfaction has become a source of worry to most organizations, including the table water business. The table water industry is one of the most competitive markets in Nigeria today. Due to the portability and affordability of table water, one sees it as a lucrative trade to venture in. However, this has also led to the proliferation of mushroom table water companies and has made it difficult for some companies to maintain their customer base. According to Elaho and Ejechi (2019), it is a lot easier to maintain an existing customer than getting a new one. It is this notion that drives pioneer table water companies to fight hard to remain relevant in the system and retain their existing customers. Despite this drive to maintain existing customers and reach out to new ones, there are still some salient issues hampering the flow of products in the pure water business. These issues include delay in product delivery, low availability of products, poor quality of products, and dissatisfaction with sales process among others.

Although previous studies (Borgman, 2018; Musari & Ayo, 2019; Mulinge, 2020; Supiandi, 2021; Iheanachor et al., 2021; Akpoviroro et al., 2020; Bou-Mitri et al., 2020) have reported significant findings pertaining to the effect of the dimensions of product features (product development, product branding and product packaging) on customer satisfaction, the results are inconsistent both in the direction and magnitude of the effect. Besides, none of these studies were conducted in the table water industry. Thus, the central focus of this study is to determine the effect of product features on customer satisfaction: an evidence from CWAY table water having in mind the following objectives:

1. Assess the effect of product development on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water.
2. Examine the effect of product branding on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water.
3. Determine the effect of product packaging on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water.

Literature review

Concept of customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction refers to customer's fulfillment of desired benefits from the product or service and verdict of accomplishment stage (Supiandi, 2021). Customer satisfaction can also be defined in terms of customer's evaluation about the differences between the cost of obtaining the product and their benefits (Elaho & Ejechi, 2019). Attainment of customer satisfaction (Oyenuga et al., 2023) is one the ultimate objective of the firm because customer satisfaction will serve as base lines for the development of long-term relationship as well as it will safe guard against the uncertainties (Leninkumar, 2017). Customer satisfaction can be high or low and its solely depends on the comparative quality of products or services i.e. high quality will lead to high satisfaction while low quality will cause low satisfaction (Hamzah & Shamsudin, 2020). Meanwhile, Kurdi et al. (2020) defined satisfaction in terms of the degree

to which products or service will meet the customer's expectations in terms of fulfillment of their needs and wants better than the competitors.

Concept of product features

Product features encompasses value addition to the product by introducing additional features that can attract customers. Customers are often willing to pay an extra shilling arising from the additional features that are added to a product. For this strategy to be successful, the market should enable proper segmentation based on the product features. Companies can implement the product features by focusing on the tastes, reliability of the product, features of the product, uniqueness and stature (Bayraktar et al., 2017). The successful implementation of this strategy is greatly dependent on the activities that are carried out in the value chain therefore within the value chain each stage must have proper value addition framework.

Product features is the fundamental goal of increasing sales and achieving a sustainable competitive advantage (Kumar et al., 2019). Product features includes all basic, short-term, and long-term activities in the field of marketing that deal with the analysis of the strategic initial situation of a company and the formulation, evaluation and selection of market-oriented strategies and therefore contributing to the goals of the company and its marketing objectives. Product features is also known as concentrated growth strategy since a company can thoroughly develop and exploit their knowledge on a specific market (Zhivov & Lohse, 2021). Companies do this so that they can expand their customer base. This is possible through size of purchase, maximum rate of product obsolescence, getting new product users, advertising and offering inducements.

The various ways of applying the product features include product development, product branding and product packaging as discussed in the next subsections.

Product development

Product development is part of a major focus and an approach by companies that seek to have a strong aspect or presence and domination in the market (Saban et al., 2015). It is part of a scheme to attain uniqueness in the products that it tries to channel out into the market. Product development aims at offering additional advantages to the customers by offering newer or additional characteristics to the products (Revilla & Knoppen, 2012). Often, the effort towards product development is aimed towards addition of different characteristics to the products, making it unique thus offering an advantage to the customer (Nduji et al., 2023). Zack et al. (2019), in their writing on product development indicate that product development can take the form of modification of the products in terms of its general presentation or still creation of an entirely new product in order to cover the interest of the targeted market thus having the direct benefit on the consumers of the product.

Product development is an interchange term with innovation of the product. Both processes assume the conversion of a product into an entirely new product or the modification for the sole purpose of fitting into the interest of the consumers (Farrell & Gallagher, 2014). Martinsuo et al. (2019), indicate that product development is often a strategy towards combating competition or trying to be ahead of the pack in the market segment. In today's business environment, competition has become rife and part of a growth strategy and market strategy is the adoption of product development and innovation.

Product Branding

An organisation that is using a product brand strategy rather than corporate branding will experience less damage to its corporate image if one of its individual brands fails (Oyenuga et al., 2021). According to Lindberg-Repo et al. (2009) the plainest definition for brand is ‘‘ the entire set of images, ideas, activities and symbols that catapults a product from being only a commodity’’. Furthermore, the concept of brand can be defined through association network. (Hollis & Brown, 2010, De Mooij, 2014) This can be interpreted as a perceptual map of various associations (both positive and negative) in the consumers’ mind. In addition, brand can be defined as a collection of perceptions that make the associated product or service more salient, interesting and compelling (Okafor & George, 2016). Furthermore, brand can be seen through its functions. Brand has several functions such as communication and competitive functions which form appropriate association to the brand and ease its differentiation from competitors (Prymon, 2016).

Product packaging

The importance of packaging is growing due to the growing self-service way of buying products. If there were no products, there would be no need for packaging either (Chen, Hung, Wang, Huang & Liao, 2017). The importance of product packaging in reaching consumers is also confirmed by Yeo et al. (2020), due to the fact that advertising is becoming less effective and the needed brand proliferation for businesses is on the rise. Product packaging and processing fluency can be a really interesting research combination (Marcus et al., 2020) since product packaging involves a lot of different elements which could be optimized in terms of processing fluency, for example the font that is used for product information, the color of that font or perhaps the color used for the product packaging itself (Alhamdi, 2020). Packaging is thus a very important element of brand equity (Oyenuga et al., 2023).

Figure 1.

Researcher’s conceptual model, 2023

Theoretical review

Resource-Based View

Resource based view RBV is a method used to achieve competitive advantage that was developed by Penrose (1995). It analysed the competitiveness of an organization using four

dimensions namely; creating competitive advantage, sustaining the competitive advantage, isolation mechanisms and competitive advantage and economic rents. The resource-based view is a decision-making outline used to establish the strategic resources that have the potential to deliver relative advantage to the firm; the resources can be utilized by an organization in order to achieve sustainable competitive advantage (Barney & Hesterly, 2010).

Conner (1991), emphasized that firm resources that are both heterogeneous and immobile, as well as possessing attributes of value, rareness, imitability and organization as a potentials source competitive advantage. This firm specific perspective can be used to build and support a case for explaining performance heterogeneity of firms in the same industry. Resources based view supposes that firms are diverse for the reason that they possess diverse resources. This means that firms employ diverse strategies due to the diverse resource mixes (Bromiley & Rau, 2016). According to Acedo et al. (2006), the important resource for an organization is the knowledge. The RBV aims to direct decision-making efforts to the resources within an organization for instance; the knowledge of employee, their abilities and competence with the possibility of achieving better performance than its competitors.

According to Peteraf and Bergen (2003), resources include both the tangible and intangible assets that an organization controls and use them to visualize and execute its strategies. Further, they argue that by controlling its resources organizations can be ahead of its competitors. More importantly, competitors may be in no position to challenge the focal organization due to the lack of similar resources. The RBV is premised on the idea that if all firms had the same quantity of resources, then the same strategy will be used by all firms therefore none will have a hedge over the other (Rumelt, 1991). Barney (2001) noted that competitive gain is felt where an organization is executing a strategy that is not being executed by the competitors at the same time. According to the resource-based theory, a firm can only sustain its competitive gains if other firms within the same market are unable to copy the strategies that are used within the firm. For this reason, a competitive advantage is not considered to exist as long as the competitors can duplicate the competitive gains. The proposition by Barney (1991) that firms are heterogeneous because they possess heterogeneous resources and by extension different strategies for exploitation of the various resource mixes can be used provide insights to performance pattern in the leather industry. RBV stresses the need to focus managerial attention on firm's internal and specific resources in an effort to identify the stock of assets, capabilities and competencies with the potential to deliver superior competitive advantage (Harney & Trehly, 2016). The theory was found to be crucial for this study since it linked the external factor of the company through the Porter generic competitive model and the external factors of the company's environment factor by the balanced scorecard (Miller, 2019). Nevertheless, when a resource is rare, scares imitable they enable a company to gain a competitive advantage. RBV serves in this research as a guideline of how the independent variables (product packaging, product development, product branding can be used to gain a competitive advantage when achieving customer satisfaction.

Research methods

The study adopted the quantitative survey research design to examine the effect of product features on customer satisfaction. The population of the study comprised of three thousand

and thirty-seven (3,037) customers of CWAY table water in Bwari Area Council, Abuja, Nigeria with a sample size of three hundred and fifty-three (353) determined using Taro Yamane's sample size statistical determination formula.

Data for this study was collected using a structured research questionnaire which was distributed to the target population and collected after a few days. Primary data was collected from the subject of study. The questionnaire was divided into five parts. The measures for the study variables were derived from past studies. Descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics provides us with the techniques of numerically and graphically presenting information that gives an overall picture of the data collected. In inferential statistics, Pearson's correlation and multiple regression analysis were used to assess both relationships and effects as per the hypotheses of the study.

Descriptive statistic for product development

The respondents of the study were asked to indicate the rate of their agreement with statements on product development and the following were the findings as shown in Table 1. The 5-point Likert scale was used, where a mean of 1.00-1.499 translates to strongly disagreed; a mean of 1.50 - 2.499 translates to disagreed; a mean of 2.50 - 3.499 translates to slightly agreed; a mean of 3.50 - 4.499 translates to agreed and a mean of 4.50 -5.00 translates to strongly agreed.

The results were as tabulated on Table 1. From the results, majority of the respondent "agreed" that CWAY Table Water offer quality and unique product/services, with a mean of 3.87 and standard deviation of 2.04. Furthermore, majority of the respondent "agreed" that "CWAY Table Water have a focus on product improvement" with a mean of 3.93 and standard deviation of 2.13. Lastly, majority of the respondent "agreed" that "CWAY Table Water has a unique taste" with a mean of 3.91 and standard deviation of 2.13.

Table 1.

Descriptive statistics for product development

Product development		SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	STD
CWAY Table Water offer quality and unique product/services	No	81	88	48	19	9	245	3.87	2.04
	%	33.20	36.07	19.67	7.79	3.69	100.41		
CWAY Table Water have a focus on product improvement	No	83	94	42	17	8	244	3.93	2.13
	%	34.02	38.52	17.21	6.97	3.28	100.00		
CWAY Table Water has a unique taste	No	89	81	47	18	9	244	3.91	2.13
	%	36.48	33.20	19.26	7.38	3.69	100.00		

Descriptive statistic for product branding

Using a 5-point Likert scale where 1.00-1.499 was strongly disagreed; 1.50 - 2.499 was disagreed; 2.50 - 3.499 was neutral; 3.50 - 4.499 was agreed and 4.50 -5.00 was strongly agreed, the respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with product branding.

Table 2.*Descriptive statistics for product branding*

Product branding		SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	STD
The brand awareness strategies of CWAY Table water have increased customers number	No	100	86	39	10	9	244	4.06	2.35
	%	40.98	35.25	15.98	4.10	3.69	100.00		
CWAY Table water has a good brand positioning.	No	92	80	52	13	7	244	3.97	2.20
	%	37.70	32.79	21.31	5.33	2.87	100.00		
CWAY Table water has a good brand image	No	83	82	55	20	4	244	3.90	2.07
	%	34.02	33.61	22.54	8.20	1.64	100.00		

The respondent's statements on product branding were assessed using five statements on five-point likert scale. The results were as tabulated on Table 2. From the results, majority of the respondent "agreed" that their "The brand awareness strategies of CWAY Table water have increased customers number" with a mean of 4.06 and standard deviation of 2.35. Additionally, majority of the respondent "agreed" that "CWAY Table water has a good brand positioning" with a mean of 3.97 and standard deviation of 2.20. Lastly, majority of the respondent "agreed" that "CWAY Table water has a good brand image" with a mean of 3.90 and standard deviation of 2.07

Results*Descriptive statistic for product packaging*

Using a 5-point Likert scale where 1.00-1.499 was strongly disagreed; 1.50 - 2.499 was disagreed; 2.50 - 3.499 was neutral; 3.50 - 4.499 was agreed and 4.50 -5.00 was strongly agreed, the respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with their organization's product packaging. The result is presented on Table 3.

The respondent's statements on product packaging were assessed using five statements on five-point likert scale. The results were as tabulated on Table 3. From the results, majority of the respondent "agreed" that "CWAY Table water offers unique packaging design", with a mean of 4.01 and standard deviation of 2.27.

Table 3.*Descriptive statistic for Product packaging*

Product packaging		SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	STD
CWAY Table water offers unique packaging design	No	95	85	45	10	9	244	4.01	2.27
	%	38.93	34.84	18.44	4.10	3.69	100.00		
The materials used in packaging CWAY Table water is of good quality	No	84	83	50	19	8	244	3.89	2.07
	%	34.43	34.02	20.49	7.79	3.28	100.00		
CWAY Table water packaging graphics like the logos are of great attraction to the customers	No	89	97	40	15	3	244	4.04	2.28
	%	36.48	39.75	16.39	6.15	1.23	100.00		

In addition, majority of the respondent “agreed” that “The materials used in packaging CWAY Table water is of good quality” with a mean of 3.89 and standard deviation of 2.07. Lastly, majority of the respondent “agreed” that “CWAY Table water packaging graphics like the logos are of great attraction to the customers” with a mean of 4.04 and standard deviation of 2.28.

Descriptive statistic for customer satisfaction

The study sought to determine the frequency of the rate of perception of customer satisfaction. Using a 5-point Likert scale where 1.00-1.499 was strongly disagreed; 1.50 - 2.499 was disagreed; 2.50 - 3.499 was not sure; 3.50 - 4.499 was agreed and 4.50 -5.00 was strongly agreed, the respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with customer satisfaction. The result is presented on Table 4.

Table 4.

Descriptive statistic for customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction		SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	STD
I feel happy about my decision concerning the choice of using CWAY Table Water	No	99	85	35	18	7	244	4.03	2.31
	%	40.57	34.84	14.34	7.38	2.87	100.00		
Considering everything, I am very satisfied with the experience I have with CWAY Table Water	No	84	94	54	7	5	244	4.00	2.21
	%	34.43	38.52	22.13	2.87	2.05	100.00		
In the future, I will be happy to use CWAY Table Water	No	98	96	32	8	10	244	4.08	2.39
	%	40.16	39.34	13.11	3.28	4.10	100.00		

From the results on Table 4, majority of the respondent “agreed” that “I feel happy about my decision concerning the choice of using CWAY Table Water” with a mean of 4.03 and standard deviation of 2.31. Moreover, majority of the respondent “agreed” that “Considering everything, I am very satisfied with the experience I have with CWAY Table Water” with a mean of 4.00 and standard deviation of 2.21. Lastly, majority of the respondent “agreed” that “In the future, I will be happy to use CWAY Table Water” with a mean of 4.08 and standard deviation of 2.39

Table 5.

Correlations between product features and customer satisfaction

	1	2	3	4
1- PD	--			
2- PB	.606**	--		
3- PP	.650**	.699**	--	
4- Customer satisfaction	.639**	.733**	.713**	--

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

PD=Product development, PB=Product branding, PP=Product packaging

The correlation analysis to determine whether product development had a significant influence on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water shows a relationship exists ($r=0.639$, $\alpha=0.00$). This implies that as product development increases customer satisfaction would increase too. The study also sought to determine whether there existed a significant relationship between product branding and customer satisfaction. The correlation analysis shows that a relationship exists ($r= 0.733$, $\alpha= 0.00$). The relationship is high suggesting that the higher product branding, the higher the customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. Finally, the correlation analysis to determine whether there was a significant association between product packaging and customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water shows that a positive relationship exists ($r = 0.731$, $\alpha = 0.00$). These findings imply that the more product packaging, the more the customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water.

Regression analysis

Regression analysis was used to test the research hypotheses. Regression analysis of all independent variables and dependent variable was done and the results were presented in tables 6 to 8.

The model summary shows the summary of the regression analysis as shown in the regression model. Below are the findings in the Table 6 below;

Table 6.

Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.798 ^a	.637	.632	.46698

a. Predictors: (Constant), product development, product packaging, product branding,

This study analyzed the effect of independent variables (product development, product branding and product packaging) on the dependent variable (customer satisfaction). The results showed that R^2 value was 0.637 hence 63.7% of the variation in the dependent variable (customer satisfaction) was explained by the variations in independent variables (product development, product branding and product packaging) as illustrated in Table 6.

Analysis of variance

The study conducted an Analysis of Variance, in order to test the effect of product features on the customer satisfaction of Veritas Table Water. The findings were as presented in Table 7.

Table 7.

Analysis of variance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	91.804	3	30.601	140.328	.000 ^b
Residual	52.337	240	.218		
Total	144.140	243			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Product development, product packaging and product branding

From Table 7, F value of 140.328 is significant at 95% confidence level. This is because the P value is less than 0.05. The strength of the variation of the predictor variables influences the dependence variable (customer satisfaction) at 0.00 significant levels. The result implies that product development, product branding and product packaging can predict customer satisfaction.

Test for coefficients

Table 8 shows the level of significance on the variables, it also provides the standardized and unstandardized coefficients.

Table 8.
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.666	.155		4.300	.000
PD	.196	.052	.200	3.763	.000
PB	.382	.054	.399	7.044	.000
PP	.259	.051	.303	5.118	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction; **PD**=Product development, **PB**=Product branding, **PP**=Product packaging

From Table 8, it can be deduced that product development ($\beta = 0.200$), product branding ($\beta = 0.399$), and product packaging ($\beta = 0.303$), are significant. This indicates that the dependent variable, customer satisfaction, would change by a corresponding number of standard deviations when product development or product branding or product packaging change by one standard deviation. These findings imply that if product packaging changed by one (1) unit, customer satisfaction would change by 0.303 units, if other factors remain fixed. In addition, the findings imply that if product branding changed by one (1) unit, customer satisfaction would change by 0.399 units, if other factors remain fixed. Lastly, the findings imply that if product development changed by one (1) unit, customer satisfaction would change by 0.200 units, if other factors remain fixed. The null hypothesis 1, 2 and 3 were therefore rejected since product development, product branding and product packaging was able to significantly influence customer satisfaction. The researcher therefore opted for alternative hypotheses.

Discussions

The general objective of the study is to determine the effect of product features on the customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. Firstly, the result of this study shows that product development has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. Product development comes as a result of changes in clients' preferences, high competition and advanced technology. These can be regarding products in the market, innovations made on the products or existing products that have been improved. Successful product development strategies are as a result of leveraging three internal elements, technical advantage and experience, marketing savvy and better understanding of the customer. (Onyango, 2016). Martinsuo et al. (2019), indicate that product development is often a

strategy towards combating competition or trying to be ahead of the pack in the market segment. In today's business environment, competition has become rife and part of a growth strategy and market strategy is the adoption of product development and innovation. This result is similar to the study of Supiandi (2021) examined the effect of product development and product quality on consumer satisfaction at PT. Gelora Cahaya Unggul in West Jakarta. This study's results show product development significantly affects consumer satisfaction. Product quality significantly affects consumer satisfaction. Product development and product quality simultaneously have a significant effect on customer satisfaction. Similarly, Iheanachor et al. (2021) investigated the impact of product development practices on the performance of new financial products and services through the analysis of ten in-depth case studies. This study finds that in Nigeria, new financial product performance is suboptimal because of poor product development practices. This study further shows that when poor execution follows inadequate product development practices, the likelihood of product failure increases, as evidenced by poor product performance and low adoption.

Secondly, product branding has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. This implies that product branding is the process of inculcating unique values to a product in order to differentiate it from competing products. Product branding signifies how an organisation distinguishes its products from similar products in the markets (Shahri, 2011). A product that is uniquely differentiated from similar products or services in a homogeneous market can offer real market benefits. The findings are in agreement with the study by Musari and Ayo (2019) examined the effectiveness of product branding on the performance of manufacturing industry using Doyin Group Nigeria Limited as a case study. The results obtained from the analysis using chi-square revealed that the product branding has a strong effect on the performance of manufacturing industry of Doyin Group Nigeria limited. Furthermore, a study by Emodi (2019) also established that brand image, brand name, brand orientation and brand loyalty have significant effect on consumer patronage of locally processed rice in South East Nigeria. The study also discovered that internal branding has no significant effect on consumer patronage of locally processed rice in South East Nigeria. The findings support the postulates of RBV on the importance of organizational strategies in value addition and increasing performance of organizations.

Thirdly, the result revealed that product packaging has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. This result implies that product packaging is one of the most important means of exchanging information about a product or service between the customer and marketers. The importance of product packaging is growing due to the growing self-service way of buying products. If there were no products, there would be no need for packaging either (Chen, Hung, Wang, Huang & Liao, 2017). The importance of product packaging in reaching consumers is also confirmed by Yeo et al. (2020), due to the fact that advertising is becoming less effective and the needed brand proliferation for businesses is on the rise. Muhammad (2016) examined the effect of store atmosphere and product packaging on consumer buying behaviour in Sports Station Mega Mall Manado. There are significant effects of store atmosphere and product packaging on consumer buying behaviour simultaneously and partially. Chen et al. (2017) examined the influence of excessive product packaging on green brand attachment and to discuss the mediation roles of green brand attitude and green brand image. Green brand attitude and green brand image fully

mediate the negative relationship between excessive product packaging and green brand attachment. Managerially, this study helps firms understand that excessive product packaging may bring damage to green brand attitude and green brand image, which positively relate to green brand attachment. Yeo et al. (2020) found a positive impact of packaging on customers' purchase intention in Malaysia.

Summary of findings

The objective of the study was to establish the effect of product features on the customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. The study adopted cross-sectional research design. The study used primary data through questionnaire. The first objective of the study was to evaluate the relationship between product development and customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. The findings from the study revealed that product development has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. The second objective of the study was to find out if product branding has any effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. The findings from the study revealed that product branding has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. The third objective of the study was to evaluate the extent to which product packaging influences customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. The finding from the study revealed that product packaging has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water.

Conclusion

The general objective of the study was to establish the effect of product features on the customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. From the findings of the study, the independent variables (product development; product branding and product packaging) had a positive effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. It was generally concluded that product features have significant effect on the customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. More specifically, first, it is concluded that there is a positive and significant effect of product development on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. In addition, the study concluded that there is a positive and significant effect of product branding on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. Lastly, the study concluded that there is a positive and significant effect of product packaging on customer satisfaction.

Recommendations

The findings from the study revealed that product development has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. This study recommends there should be very strong emphasis on the development of new and innovative products. It is recommended that management of CWAY Table Water should promote activities relating to product design, product improvement, product functionality and product performance through embracing innovative ideas, monitoring and responding to the changes in the needs of the customers and adequate committing resources for product development.

The findings from the study revealed that product branding has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. The study recommended that management of CWAY Table Water to embrace all the indicators of product branding to be

able optimally maximize its benefits. The management can invest more resources on this variable, noting that branding is one of the key elements in today's market which greatly influence the performance of a company. They can achieve this by ensuring that the employees are well trained to know the best and upcoming branding ideas and skills, which can attract more customers, thus increase performance. However, the management should also think outside the box to keep pace with new and dynamic environment in the CWAY Table Water industry.

The finding from the study revealed that product packaging has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of CWAY Table Water. On the basis of the findings, it is recommended that CWAY Table Water must invest more in promotional activities relating to design, colour, material quality and logo which is critical in ensuring packaging design is achieved in improving performance. The management should embrace innovative ideas, monitoring and responding to the changes in the needs of the customers. Packaging design was found to have a positive effect on the company needs and more also the logo and the color which have the highest mean showing they have greater potential in improving performance.

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